

Determination of Some Organic Compounds by Oxidation with Trivalent Copper

SAMEER BOSE* and MISS NIRMALA NAIR

Department of Chemistry, University of Jabalpur, Jabalpur

Manuscript received 1 October 1973; accepted 13 February 1974

A procedure has been described for the determination of some simple organic compounds by oxidation with potassium diperiodato and ditellurato cuprate (III). Samples were treated at 30° to 100°, in alkaline medium with an excess of the oxidant, which was back estimated after completion of reaction, by titration with a standard solution of arsenite. The results are precise to about 0.5%. An adverse effect of high alkalinity, on the stability of the reagent, has also been demonstrated.

THE strong oxidative power of trivalent copper has been used for the oxidimetric determination of both inorganic and organic compounds¹⁻⁶.

Standardization of copper(III) reagents has been a subject of much attention. The direct titrimetric method of Beck¹ consists in titration of a standard solution of glucose with copper(III) reagent to the appearance of a transient green coloration, stable for about 30 secs. Eight equivalents of copper (III) were consumed for each mole of glucose. Keyworth and Stone⁷ found the appearance of the transient green coloration unsuitable and not to be a true indication of the end point. Chandra and Yadava⁵ have shown this standardization procedure faulty, as glucose consumes as much as 24 equivalents of the oxidant depending on the experimental conditions. The same authors developed a modified procedure for standardizing ditelluratocuprate(III) solution consisting in treating an aliquot of the reagent with an excess of arsenite solution and allowing it to stay for 3-4 mins. It was then acidified with sulfuric acid to the disappearance of the green suspension; a clear and acidic solution, thus resulted, was treated with an excess of bicarbonate and the unused arsenite back titrated with standard iodine. However, diperiodato-cuprate(III) can not be determined by this procedure as periodate is also as strong an oxidizing agent in this medium.

A simple visual titrimetric method has been adopted in this study on the oxidation of some organic compounds by ditellurato- and diperiodato cuprate (III), and was found to be very satisfactory with both the reagents.

Experimental

Reagents :

A 0.05 *M* solution of diperiodato cuprate(III) was prepared⁸ by oxidizing copper(II) sulfate with potassium peroxydisulfate in alkaline medium and in the

presence of potassium periodate. Solution of ditellurato cuprate(III) was similarly prepared using tellurate instead of periodate.

Standardization of Cu(III) reagents :

An aliquot of the copper (III) reagent was taken in a 150 ml Erlenmeyer flask and titrated with a 0.025 *N* solution of arsenite, taken in a 10 ml burette, to a greenish-blue end point being stable for about 30 secs and then turning to the blue color of copper(II). The end point is sharp and reproducible and since titration is carried out in an alkaline medium (2*N*) the interference from periodate does not occur.

Samples :

All of the organic samples tested were A.R. grade. Their solutions were prepared by dissolving a right amount of the sample in distilled water.

All other chemicals were reagent grade

Procedure :

An aliquot of the sample containing 5-50 mg of organic material was pipetted into a 150 ml flask and to this added a 0.05 *M* solution of trivalent copper, about 50% in excess. The flask was attached to a ground-glass joint air condenser and suspended in a hot water-bath (Table 1). After the completion of reaction, the flask was cooled, walls of condenser washed with 5-10 ml of 2*N* potassium hydroxide solution and the residual oxidant was back titrated with a 0.025 *N* solution of arsenite by the method described before. Alternatively, the residual reagent can be evaluated by adding 5 gms of potassium iodide along with sufficient 2*N* sulfuric acid to neutralize the alkali, and titrating the liberated iodine with standard thiosulfate. The arsenite titration is, however, better in as much as it eliminates the use of large amounts of costly potassium iodide and accounts for the oxidative power due only to trivalent copper.

* Present address : 310, Napier Town, Jabalpur.

A blank determination was similarly performed.

Results and Discussion

In Table 1, are summarized the reaction conditions used for determining various organic compounds of general occurrence by oxidation with potassium diperiodatocuprate(III); the numbers of equivalents of Cu(III) consumed, in each case are also mentioned. All of the results reported are average of six determinations and arsenite back titration method was adopted for final analytical finish. Results obtained using tellurate complex were in agreement within 0.3% with the reported results, and the accuracy of the procedure was practically undisturbed when the residual oxidant was evaluated iodimetrically.

TABLE 1—OXIDATION OF SOME ORGANIC COMPOUNDS WITH POTASSIUM DIPERIODATO CUPRATE (III)

Organic substrate	Reaction conditions		Number of eqs. of Cu(III) consumed per mole of reductant
	Temp. (°C)	Time (mins)	
Mandelic acid	40	30	4.0
Lactic acid	50	120	4.0
	100	120	12.0
Pyruvic acid	30	20	2.0
	100	120	10.0
Formic acid	70	240	2.0
Acrylic acid	70	240	4.0
	100	360	12.0
Monochloroacetic acid	100	240	6.0
Ascorbic acid	100	120	20.0
Glucose	100	60	24.1
Fructose	100	60	24.0
Galactose	100	60	24.2
Sucrose	100	60	48.1
Lactose	100	60	48.0

A perusal of data presented in Table 1, reveals that at lower temperatures mandelic acid is oxidized to benzoic acid, and lactic, pyruvic and acrylic acid to acetic acid, along with carbon dioxide (and water in the case of lactic acid). At boiling water-bath temperature, lactic, pyruvic, formic, acrylic and

ascorbic acid and all carbohydrates studied, are oxidized to carbon dioxide and water; with monochloroacetic acid, hydrochloric acid is one of the reaction products with carbon dioxide and water. Benzoate and acetate⁹ ions were tested in the oxidation products of the compounds concerned.

Although Cu(III) in both the forms, as periodate and tellurate complex, can be used for determining various organic substances, the use of potassium diperiodato-cuprate(III) is recommended, as it is more stable at ordinary and high temperatures. It has also been found in these studies that alkali concentration has a marked effect on the strength and stability of Cu(III) complexes. The alkali concentration should be kept at about 2N in all the oxidations with Cu(III). Higher alkali concentration decreases the strength and stability of the reagent and this appears to be due to the formation of cupric hydroxide and its oxide. A greenish-black precipitate of cupric hydroxide and cupric oxide was eventually separated from a solution of reagent of high alkalinity when stored for some days.

References

1. G. BECK, *Mikrochem.*, 1950, 35, 169.
2. G. BECK, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 9, 241.
3. G. BECK, *Mikrochem.*, 1951, 36/37, 245
4. S. CHANDRA and K. L. YADAVA, *Talanta*, 1968, 15, 349.
5. S. CHANDRA and K. L. YADAVA, *Microchem. J.*, 1968, 13, 491
6. S. CHANDRA and K. L. YADAVA, *Microchem. J.*, 1968, 13, 586.
7. D. A. KEYWORTH and K. G. STONE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 27, 833.
8. A. BERKA, J. VULTERIN and J. ZYKA, "Newer Redox Titrants", Pergamon, Oxford, 1965, p. 15.
9. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 1948, p. 305.